

Utilizing Agro-residues for Green Synthesis and Characterization of Sulfur Nanoparticles and Microparticles: A Preliminary Investigation

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Abstract

Bio-inspired green synthesis of nanoparticle synthesis is superior to physical and chemical methods, which are more expensive, toxic and dangerous, endangering the ecosystem and human health. In the current study, orange and garlic peels were used to synthesize sulphur nanoparticles (SNPs) and microparticles in a single step, utilizing a green technique. UV/visible spectroscopy was used to characterize the biosynthesis of SNPs prior to spectroscopy. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) Spectroscopy was used to determine size of nanoparticles/microparticles, while Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to characterize SNPs. Using UV-VIS spectroscopy, the study's findings showed that orange peels had an absorption spectrum at 264 nm, which is a feature of SNP production. However, there was no clear distinct peak indicating formation of SNPs using garlic peels. FTIR spectra of SNPs and control (orange peel extract) exhibited broad intense peaks at 1010.1 cm⁻¹ and 1028.7 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicating a marginal shift and presence of flavanones (polyphenols) adsorbed on the surface of the nanoparticles. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) Spectroscopy results showed dimension of nanoparticles within the range of 15 to 80nm and 100 to 400nm for microparticles. In conclusion, orange peels degraded with citric acid alone, has the potential to synthesize SNPs nanoparticles and microparticles for variety of uses in environmental, cosmetic and medicinal sectors. Further investigations should focus on parametric modification and optimization of SNPs including high throughput characterization techniques.

Keywords: Green synthesis, sulphur nanoparticles, microparticles, orange peels, garlic peels

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Introduction

Development of effective green chemistry for nanoparticle production has drawn huge attention from researchers recently; coupled with been sustainable, cost-effective, non-toxic, convenient, green, and eco-friendly. Utilizing

organisms to fabricate nanoparticles is gaining utmost focus among scientists. Plants appear most promising, for large-scale nanoparticles production. In comparison to microorganisms, plants synthesize nanoparticles at higher rate

coupled with greater stability (Ahmed et al., 2019).

Furthermore, plant-based nanoparticles differ in size and shape (Ghotekar et al., 2020). Moreover, numerous phytoconstituents found in plants, namely: alkaloids, alcohols, amino acids, vitamins, polysaccharides, proteins and enzymes confers bio-reduction efficacy, synthesis and stability of nanoparticles (Ahmed et al., 2019).

Among several types of non-metal nanoparticles (NPs), Sulphur nanoparticles (SNPs) deem to be fascinating. However, production of toxic wastes, unpleasant by-products and disastrous contaminants through physical or chemical means, poses challenges regarding SNP synthesis. Green synthesis (plant-mediated biosynthesis) of SNPs, is the most effective way to reduce or eliminate harmful chemicals. Owing to their exceptional performance and selectivity, eco-benevolent SNPs have been recognized as valuable nanomaterials in numerous sectors; namely, agricultural, biomedical and catalytic applications, such as lithium-sulphur batteries, pesticides, fungicides, carbon nanotube modification, gas sensors, neutron capture in cancer therapy (Ghotekar et al., 2020).

Large surface areas and distinct nanosizes are two peculiar characteristics of sulphur nanoparticles (SNPs). Compared to various non-metallic nanoparticles and bulk sulfur particles (BSPs), these characteristics increase their attractiveness towards development of carbon nanotubes and pharmaceuticals (Yuan et al., 2021). Recently, Hasan et al. (2024), opined that sulfur nanoparticles were successfully produced from aqueous extract of *Ziziphus spina* tree leaves; indicated by a strong FTIR peak at 460 cm^{-1} .

To synthesize sulphur nanoparticles, *Azadirachta indica* was also used as bio-reductant. According to dynamic light scattering measurements, SNPs had a particle size of 35–40 nm. FT-IR spectrum revealed a distinctive wavenumber absorption between 3384.73 cm^{-1} and 533.56 cm^{-1} . UV-visible spectrophotometer's absorption spectra fell between 200 and 800 nm (Choudhary et al., 2023). Accordingly, green synthesized SNPs using *Cannabis* plant extract revealed an average size of 20 nm when characterized via UV-VIS Spectroscopy, SEM, TEM, HRTEM and FTIR (Dasauni et al., 2024).

Citrus peels in general and orange peels in particular are great sources of natural bioactive substances, including pectin, fibers, minerals, essential oils, polyphenols and monosaccharides (Ben Hsouna et al., 2023). Pectin (heteropolysaccharide) ranges in size from 80 to 400 kDa and contains a significant amount of galacturonic acid. It is a valuable by-product of citrus peels with high nutraceutical value, utilized as a stabilizer, gelling agent and thickening agent in food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries (Ciriminna et al., 2017; Senit et al., 2019). Orange peels can be harnessed as rich natural resource because they contain valuable biologically active components (Liu et al., 2021).

Additionally, garlic by-products from industrial processing present both financial and environmental challenges. Garlic peels has been a primary challenge constituting about 24% its total weight. To date, it has been hardly examined and is typically thrown away (Chaudhary et al., 2021). According to some reports, this by-product has biological activities, such as antioxidant capacity (Naqvi et al., 2020; Pardede et al., 2020; Al-Defiery et al., 2021; Singiri et al., 2022).

However, to the best of the authors knowledge, green synthesis of SNPs harnessing potential of orange and garlic peel extracts have not been evaluated yet. Therefore, our research focus was based on utilizing underutilized sulphur-rich agroresidues like orange and garlic peels for green synthesis of sulphur nanoparticles (SNPs), adopting 'conversion of waste to wealth' concept *vis-à-vis* its particulate characterization.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Conical flask, beaker, glass rod, water bath, weighing balance, measuring cylinder, test tubes, test tube racks, nitric acid (HNO_3), hydrochloric acid (HCl), sodium thiosulphate pentahydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$), distilled water, deionized water, Centrifuge, UV-Vis Spectrophotometer, FTIR Spectrometer and DLS Spectrometer.

METHODS

Preparation of Plant Extract

Allium sativum (garlic) and *Citrus sinensis* (orange) were procured from Samaru in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. Identification and authentication of plant samples was done at the Herbarium Unit, department of Botany, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, where voucher specimen numbers ABU0232 (*Allium sativum*) and ABU0990 (*Citrus sinensis*) were deposited. They were carefully washed under running water and subsequently washed with water (deionized) to remove dust and other materials. Agro-residue was obtained by peeling, followed by shade-drying at room temperature for a period of three (3) weeks and subsequent grinding using a blender. Each plant material (20g) was dispersed into 100ml deionized water in 200ml Erlenmeyer flask. The mixture was boiled at 100 degrees Celsius for 2 hours and then filtered using muslin cloth. The filtrate solution was used as the desired plant extract (Tripathi et al., 2018).

Synthesis of Sulphur Nanoparticles (SNPs)

To remove any potential nucleation sites prior to synthesizing sulfur nanoparticles, all glasswares were cleaned using an aqua regia solution (3:1 nitric acid v/v and hydrochloric acid). Initially, 50 milliliters of deionized water was used to entirely dissolve sodium thiosulfate pentahydrate (0.078M); forming a solution. The said solution was then supplemented with 20 milliliters of each plant extract. 25 milliliters of 20% citric acid solution was added to the previous reaction mixture after five minutes of constant stirring. A precipitate was seen after the mixture had been continuously stirred, sporadically, for an hour. Centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 30minutes was employed to collect the precipitate following washing with deionized water at 2000rpm for 30minutes. Synthesized SNP solution was oven-dried at 100°C until dehydrated, to obtain dried powder. Experiments on SNPs synthesis for both orange and garlic peels were conducted in triplicates (Tripathi et al., 2018; Choudhary et al., 2023).

Experimental Grouping

Table 1: Experimental grouping and sample composition of orange and garlic peels

EXPERIMENTAL GROUPING	SAMPLE COMPOSITION		
	ORANGE PEELS		
Group 1 (Orange nanoparticles SNPs)	50ml sodium thiosulphate pentahydrate	20ml orange-peels extract	25ml citric acid (20%)
Group 2 (Positive control)		20ml orange-peels extract	25ml citric acid (20%)
Group 3 (negative control)		20ml orange-peels extract	
GARLIC PEELS			
Group 4 (garlic nanoparticles SNPs)	50ml sodium thiosulphate pentahydrate	20ml garlic-peels extract	25ml citric acid (20%)
Group 5 (Positive control)		20ml garlic-peels extract	25ml citric acid (20%)
Group 6 (negative control)		20ml garlic-peels extract	

Characterization of Sulphur nanoparticles (SNPs) by UV-Vis, FTIR and DLS spectroscopy

As-synthesized SNPs were initially characterized using UV-Vis spectroscopy (Cary 300 Agilent series), with scanning range of 200–700 nm. Biomolecules present on SNPs were analyzed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Cary 630 Agilent series). For FTIR measurements, the colloidal suspension of SNPs was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min and orange-peel pellet was washed four times to remove impurities. The range in which spectra were recorded was 600–

4000 cm^{-1} . SNPs were also analyzed using Dynamic Light Scattering Spectroscopy (DLS-Malvern ZetaSizer, ZEN1600 Instrument, UK) to identify possible size and range of synthesized nanomaterial.

Results

Figure 1 shows the UV-Vis spectrum of SNPs. The peak at 264 nm in figure 1 indicates the successful formation of SNPs. However, there was no clear distinct peak indicating formation of sulphur nanoparticles for garlic peels as depicted in figure 2.

Fig 1 and 2: UV-Vis absorption spectrum of biosynthesized SNPs by orange peels at 262nm (left) and garlic peels at 270nm (right).

The synthesized SNPs / microparticles were scanned by FTIR spectroscopy in the range of 600–4000 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3 and 4). The FTIR spectrum of the control (orange peel filtrate) exhibited absorption bands at 2855.1 cm^{-1} ,

2,922.2 cm^{-1} , 1230.0 cm^{-1} and 1524.5 cm^{-1} . Whereas in the spectrum of SNPs, absorption bands appeared at 2851.4 cm^{-1} , 1226.3 cm^{-1} and 1,796.6 cm^{-1} . Spectra of SNPs and control extract both exhibited broad intense peaks at 1010.1 cm^{-1} and 1028.7 cm^{-1} , respectively.

Fig 3: FTIR spectrum of biosynthesized Sulphur-Nanoparticles (SNPs) using orange peels.

Fig 4: FTIR spectrum of biosynthesized particles using orange peels filtrate alone (control)

Figure 5 and 6 shows the DLS (dynamic light scattering) spectra of as-synthesized microparticles and SNPs respectively. Results obtained showed bulk of synthesized particles

were within the range of 100-800nm. Synthesis of SNPs using citric acid alone revealed nanoparticles with dimension within the range of 15-80nm (Figure 6).

Fig 5: Dynamic light scattering spectra of SNPs synthesized using orange peels. All particles appeared as microparticles within the range of 100-400nm.

Fig 6: Dynamic light scattering spectra of particles synthesized from orange peels using citric acid as the degrading agent (control). Sulphur Nanoparticles (SNPs) appeared between 15-80nm (left) while microparticles appeared within 100-800nm (right).

Discussion

Spectroscopy, a technique rooted on interaction between light and matter is widely utilized for measuring intensity of light; which is proportional to its wavelength. It is utilized to ascertain stability and formation of SNPs at the preliminary stage. UV-Visible Spectroscopy entails absorption of ultraviolet light or visible light by chemical compounds, resulting in distinct spectra formation (Choudhary et al., 2023). α -sulfur is known to have an optical absorption maximum (λ_{Max}) between 260 and 280 nm (Heatley and Page, 1952). The peak at 264 nm for orange peels indicates successful formation of SNPs. A secondary peak at 327 nm corresponds to b2-e3 transition (Richardson and Weinberger, 1975; Dasauni et al., 2024). However, there was no clear distinct peak indicating formation of sulphur nanoparticles for garlic peels.

To enable determination of SNPs functional group, FTIR analysis was performed on both SNPs (orange peels and citric acid) sample and control (orange peel filtrate). The FTIR spectrum of the control exhibited a prominent peak at 2855.1 cm^{-1} , whereas in the spectrum of SNPs, this peak shifted to 2851.4 cm^{-1} , indicating $-\text{OH}$ stretching (Tripathi et al., 2019). The C-H stretching of CH_2 and CH_3 is represented by the peak in the control spectrum at $2,922.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Mehrotra et al., 2017). Nevertheless, there was no peak in the SNPs' spectrum at $2,922.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating that the C-H stretching vibration was involved in the SNPs' creation. A peak that corresponded to the aldehyde group $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching in SNPs sample was seen at

$1,796.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The N-H stretching vibration in the protein's amide bonds was represented by a peak in the control spectra at 1524.5 cm^{-1} , which was absent in SNPs. The band at 1230.0 cm^{-1} for the control extract appeared at 1226.3 cm^{-1} for SNPs, which corresponds to the S=O stretching of organic sulphates like sulfones, sulfonyl chloride and sulfonamide (Tripathi et al., 2019). Spectra of SNPs and control extract exhibited broad intense peaks at 1010.1 and 1028.7 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating a marginal shift. The presence of flavanones adsorbed on the nanoparticle surface is indicated by a representative peak at $1,074 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Shankar et al., 2004).

Results obtained from DLS spectroscopy showed bulk of as-synthesized particles were within the range of 100-800nm on nanoscale, hence do not fall under the conventional range of nanoparticles (1-100nm). However, they fall within the upper range of microparticles. Moreover, synthesis of SNPs using citric acid alone revealed nanoparticles with dimension within the range of 15-80nm; this commemorates previous studies (Paralikar and Rai, 2017; Usman et al., 2025). Leaves of *Acanthephylum bracteatum* also revealed SNPs with dimension of 40nm (Kouzegaran and Farhadi, 2017). Previous researches reported SNPs with narrow size range of 2-15nm for *Ficus benghalensis* leaves (Tripathi et al., 2019) and 20nm for *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves (Albanna et al., 2016). However, larger sized SNPs were also reported at 89nm for *Azadirachta indica*, 95nm for *Mangifera indica*, 86nm for *Catharanthus roseus* (Paralikar and Rai, 2017).

Biosynthesis mechanism

Fig 7: Mechanistic representation of biosynthesis of SNPs from orange peel extract (adopted from Tripathi et al., 2018)

Possible mechanism of biosynthesis of SNPs is described in Figure 7. All plant components, including leaves, fruits, peels, seeds and flowers, are rich in polyphenolics, which work well as reducing agents to limit reactive oxygen species (ROS). Orange peels have a prominent abundance of polyphenolic compounds (Ben Hsouna et al., 2023). Combination of phytochemicals and citric acid results in disproportionation process causes the phytochemicals to instantly reduce S^{6+} to S^0 and citric acid to oxidize S^{2-} to S^0 . After that, S^0 goes through a nucleation process to achieve its ideal size and form, which is impacted by several factors like temperature, pH and the type of reducing and capping agent (Tripathi et al., 2019; Tripathi and Chung, 2019).

Conclusion

Sulphur nanoparticles and microparticles were synthesized from orange peels and characterized. The dimension of the particles was within the range of 15-80nm for nanoparticles as well as 100-400nm for microparticles. Hence, in conclusion, orange peels degraded with citric acid alone, has the potential to synthesize SNPs nanoparticles and microparticles for variety of uses in the environmental, cosmetic and medicinal sectors. Future research will focus on bulk synthesis by prolonging the reaction time and diversifying concentration of the starting plant material. Also, more imaging technique will be employed *vis-à-vis* application of the synthesized sulphur nanoparticles for practical utilization.

Funding Statement

None.

Conflict of Interest

None.

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Author's contribution

Conceptualization: HSU, ABS, AS; Laboratory experiments: MOA, HSU; Data Analysis: HSU, MOA; Writing- drafting original manuscript: HSU,

MOA; Writing-review and editing: HSU, MOA, FA, MID, ABS, AS; Resources: HSU, MOA, FA, MID; Supervision: HSU, ABS, AS. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

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